

CERTIFICATE OF INTERNSHIP

This Certifies that

Anusha S Pawar

*Has successfully completed the Internship Programme on Mobile App
Development on Flutter Framework*

15 September 2021

Shaan SK

DATE

MANAGING DIRECTOR

HEXNBIT

"SKILLING FOR FUTURE"

INDUSTRY PARTNER – TEVATRON TECHNOLOGIES PVT LTD

HexnBit
Skilling for Future

Reference Unique ID: HNB0809211943

Date: 08/09/2021

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. Anvitha Kotian** from **Srinivas University College Of Engineering & Technology** has undergone and completed her Training & Internship Program in "VLSI Design" from 19th July 2021 to 30th August 2021.

During this period, exposure has been given on various technical activities around "VLSI" technology at Tevatron Technologies Pvt. Ltd.

We found her extremely inquisitive & hardworking. She was very much interested to learn the function of our core division & also willing to put her extra effort to get into the depth of the subject in order to understand it better. Her overall performance has been rated very Good & we would like to wish her for future endeavors.

Regards,

Gagan
Preet Singh

Digitally signed by
Gagan Preet Singh
Date: 2021.09.10
15:48:52 +05'30'

For. Hexnbit

For Tevatron Technologies Pvt Ltd

ZEPHYR
Technologies & Solutions Pvt. Ltd.

ZTP-INT-2020-200603

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate is presented to **Mr. Dhanush A Uchil (ISU18EC005)**, student of **Srinivas University College of Engineering and Technology Mukka, Mangalore** for successfully completing the internship in **Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning** under the guidance of our special team of trainers.

Period of Internship Training: **22-07-2021 to 22-08-2021**

We have found him to be a self starter who is motivated, duty bound and Hard-working. He worked sincerely on him assignments, and him performance was Par Excellence.

Date: 10-09-2021

Zephyr Technologies and Solutions Pvt Ltd

Place: Mangaluru

Abdulla Abid Samah
Chief Executive Officer

mail@zephyrtechnologies.in

0824 4250227, 8111843307, 9961234515

Registered Office:

Door No 18208/D3, III Floor, Golden Chambers, Kandamkulam, P.O Calicut - 673002

Head Office:

GS2, Heavenly Plaza, Suite No.352, Kakkanad, Kochi, Kerala - 682021

Regional Office:

IInd Floor, Oberle Towers, Balmatta, Mangaluru, Karnataka - 575002

www.zephyrtechnologies.in

HEXNBIT

"SKILLING FOR FUTURE"

INDUSTRY PARTNER – TEVATRON TECHNOLOGIES PVT LTD

HexnBit
Skilling for Future

Reference Unique ID: HNB2108211949

Date:21/08/2021

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. Gururaj** from **Srinivas University, College Of Engineering & Technology** has undergone and completed his Training & Internship Program in "Web Development" from 4th July 2021 to 15th August 2021.

During this period, exposure has been given on various technical activities around "Web Development" technology at Tevatron Technologies Pvt. Ltd.

We found him extremely inquisitive & hardworking. He was very much interested to learn the function of our core division & also willing to put his extra effort to get into the depth of the subject in order to understand it better. His overall performance has been rated very Good & we would like to wish him for future endeavors.

Regards,

Gagan
Preet Singh

Digitally signed by
Gagan Preet Singh
Date: 2021.08.26
19:14:37 +05'30'

For. Hexnbit

For Tevatron Technologies Pvt Ltd

ZEPHYR
Technologies & Solutions Pvt. Ltd.

ZTP-INT-2020-200603

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate is presented to Ms. Harshitha V (1SU18EC008), student of Srinivas University College of Engineering and Technology Mukka, Mangalore for successfully completing the internship in Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning under the guidance of our special team of trainers.

Period of Internship Training: 22-07-2021 to 22-08-2021

We have found her to be a self starter who is motivated, duty bound and Hard-working. She worked sincerely on her assignments, and her performance was Par Excellence.

Date: 10-09-2021

Zephyr Technologies and Solutions Pvt Ltd

Place: Mangaluru

Abdulla Abid Samah
Chief Executive Officer

 0824 4250227, 8111843307, 9961234515

Registered Office:
Door No 18208/D3, III Floor, Golden Chambers, Kandamkulam, P.O Calicut - 673002

Head Office:
GS2, Heavenly Plaza, Suite No.352, Kakkanad, Kochi, Kerala - 682021

Regional Office:
IInd Floor, Oberle Towers, Balmatta, Mangaluru, Karnataka - 575002

www.zephyrtechnologies.in

NITK-09-113

INDUSTRIAL INTERNSHIP PROGRAM 2021

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

THIS IS TO CERTIFY THAT

Pavan kumara s u

FROM Srinivas university, college of Engineering and Technology,
Surathakal

DEPARTMENT OF Electronics and Communication Engineering

HAS PARTICIPATED AND COMPLETED THE **1 MONTH INTERNSHIP**

PROGRAM ON **Embedded Systems**

IEEE SB CHAPTER, NITK and PANTECH E LEARNING

SRINIVASAN N

DIRECTOR - PANTECH E LEARNING

Dr.P.VENKATESA PERUMAL

PROFESSOR - INCHARGE - NITK - STEP

Duration of Internship

13.09.2021

To 15.10.2021

ZEPHYR
Technologies & Solutions Pvt. Ltd.

ZTP-INT-2020-200603

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

This certificate is presented to Ms. Poornima (1SU18EC010), student of Srinivas University College of Engineering and Technology Mukka, Mangalore for successfully completing the internship in Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning under the guidance of our special team of trainers.

Period of Internship Training: 22-07-2021 to 22-08-2021

We have found her to be a self starter who is motivated, duty bound and Hard-working. She worked sincerely on her assignments, and her performance was Par Excellence.

Date: 10-09-2021

Zephyr Technologies and Solutions Pvt Ltd

Place: Mangaluru

Abdulla Abid Samah
Chief Executive Officer

mail@zephyrtechnologies.in 0824 4250227, 8111843307, 9961234515

Registered Office:
Door No 18208/D3, III Floor, Golden Chambers, Kandamkulam, P.O Calicut - 673002

Head Office:
G52, Heavenly Plaza, Suite No.352, Kakkanad, Kochi, Kerala - 682021

Regional Office:
IInd Floor, Oberle Towers, Balmatta, Mangaluru, Karnataka - 575002

www.zephyrtechnologies.in

CERTIFICATE OF INTERNSHIP

This Certifies that

Rida Fathima Sheikh

*Has successfully completed the Internship Programme on Mobile App
Development on Flutter Framework*

Sham SK

30 September 2021

DATE

MANAGING DIRECTOR

HEXNBIT

"SKILLING FOR FUTURE"

INDUSTRY PARTNER – TEVATRON TECHNOLOGIES PVT LTD

Hex
BIT
Skilling for Future

Reference Unique ID: HNB0809211942

Date: 08/09/2021

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. Roshan Shetty** from **Srinivas University College Of Engineering & Technology** has undergone and completed his Training & Internship Program in "**VLSI Design**" from 19th July 2021 to 30th August 2021.

During this period, exposure has been given on various technical activities around "**VLSI**" technology at Tevatron Technologies Pvt. Ltd.

We found him extremely inquisitive & hardworking. He was very much interested to learn the function of our core division & also willing to put his extra effort to get into the depth of the subject in order to understand it better. His overall performance has been rated very Good & we would like to wish him for future endeavors.

Regards,

Gagan
Preet Singh

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Gagan Preet Singh
Date: 2021.09.10
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For. Hexnbit

For Tevatron Technologies Pvt Ltd

HEXNBIT

"SKILLING FOR FUTURE"

INDUSTRY PARTNER – TEVATRON TECHNOLOGIES PVT LTD

Reference Unique ID: HNB2108211934

Date: 21/08/2021

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. Sachin** from **Srinivas University, College Of Engineering & Technology** has undergone and completed his Training & Internship Program in "**Web Development**" from 4th July 2021 to 15th August 2021.

During this period, exposure has been given on various technical activities around "**Web Development**" technology at Tevatron Technologies Pvt. Ltd.

We found him extremely inquisitive & hardworking. He was very much interested to learn the function of our core division & also willing to put his extra effort to get into the depth of the subject in order to understand it better. His overall performance has been rated very Good & we would like to wish him for future endeavors.

Regards,

Gagan
Preet Singh

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Gagan Preet Singh
Date: 2021.08.26
19:23:28 +05'30'

For. Hexnbit

For Tevatron Technologies Pvt Ltd

HEXNBIT

"SKILLING FOR FUTURE"

INDUSTRY PARTNER - TEVATRON TECHNOLOGIES PVT LTD

HexnBit
Skilling for Future

Reference Unique ID: HNB0909211931

Date: 09/09/2021

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. **Sammed Subhas Danolli** from **Srinivas University College Of Engineering & Technology** has undergone and completed his Internship Program in "Embedded Systems-STM32 (ARM)" from 26th July 2021 to 6th September 2021.

During this period, exposure has been given on various technical activities around "Embedded Systems-STM32 (ARM)" technology at Tevatron Technologies Pvt. Ltd. He has successfully done a project on "Temperature and Humidity Monitoring System".

We found him extremely inquisitive & hardworking. He was very much interested to learn the function of our core division & also willing to put his extra effort to get into the depth of the subject in order to understand it better. His overall performance has been rated very Good & we would like to wish him for future endeavors.

Regards,

Gagan
Preet Singh

For, Hexnbit

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Gagan Preet Singh
Date: 2021.10.09
18:45:58 +05'30'

For Tevatron Technologies Pvt Ltd

HEXNBIT

"SKILLING FOR FUTURE"

INDUSTRY PARTNER – TEVATRON TECHNOLOGIES PVT LTD

Reference Unique ID: HNB0809211930

Date: 08/09/2021

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. Sanath M** from **Srinivas University College Of Engineering & Technology** has undergone and completed his Training & Internship Program in "VLSI Design" from 19th July 2021 to 30th August 2021.

During this period, exposure has been given on various technical activities around "VLSI" technology at Tevatron Technologies Pvt. Ltd.

We found him extremely inquisitive & hardworking. He was very much interested to learn the function of our core division & also willing to put his extra effort to get into the depth of the subject in order to understand it better. His overall performance has been rated very Good & we would like to wish him for future endeavors.

Regards,

Gagan
Preet Singh

Digitally signed by
Gagan Preet Singh
Date: 2021.09.10
15:47:27 +05'30'

For. Hexnbit

For Tevatron Technologies Pvt Ltd

Reference Unique ID:HNB1810211926

Date: 18/10/2021

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. Sriprada** from **Srinivas University College Of Engineering & Technology** has undergone and completed his Training & Internship Program in "VLSI Design" from 19th July to 2021 to 30th August 2021.

During this period, exposure has been given on various technical activities around "VLSI" technology at Tevatron Technologies Pvt. Ltd. He has successfully done a Project on "One Cross Three Router".

We found him extremely inquisitive & hardworking. He was very much interested to learn the function of our core division & also willing to put his extra effort to get into the depth of the subject in order to understand it better. His overall performance has been rated very Good & we would like to wish him for future endeavors.

Regards,

Gagan
Preet Singh

Digitally signed by
Gagan Preet Singh
Date: 2021.10.23
17:16:58 +05'30'

For. Hexnbit

For. Tevatron Technologies Pvt Ltd

Official member to

CERTIFICATE OF INTERNSHIP

This is to certify that **Vinayak** has successfully completed **4 weeks (or 140 hrs)** Java Coding Internship.

- 1) Consumer Loan Assistant Project
- 2) Home Inventory Manager Project

The projects were assessed by AI Engine trained by mentors as listed on <https://mentor.suvenconsultants.com>

Your performance was **Noteworthy** - 🏆🏆🏆🏆 in the Online Internship. Wishing you all the best for more internships and a great career.

Your Internship Profile can be viewed on <https://internship.suvenconsultants.com/user?u=dmluYXlhaz21lc3RoYT12OEEBzY3RwZA==>

Rocky Jagtiani

Domain Expert: Rocky Jagtiani
Technical Head - SCTPL
<https://suvenconsultants.com>

Date of Issue: 30-08-2021

This is auto generated by our ai engine

Niraj Sharma

Domain Expert: Niraj Sharma
UI/UX expert and Software Engineer
NeoSOFT Technologies

Tarik Sheth

Domain Expert: Tarik Sheth
MCP,HP(AIS),CSTE,CSQA,CSTM
VP(in Investment Banking MNC)

Companies Recruiting

... & Many More